

Level of Community Knowledge Regarding the Management of Disposal Mask Waste in Tanjungpinang Barat Sub-District, Tanjungpinang Barat

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Abstract

Introduction: Wearing a mask has become a daily primary need for many people during the Covid-19 pandemic and caused significant increase of disposable masks. A large number of masks used creates new problems, if not managed properly will impact the environment. **Purpose:** this study aimed knowledge of community regarding the management of disposal masks waste. **Methods:** This is a analytic observational with a cross-sectional study design approach. Datas collected using questionnaires survey. The variables were age, gender, education, occupation, and waste management of masks. The number of population are 2557 families and 346 samples were chosen using proportional random sampling with standards aged 15-64 years, willing to be respondents, and able to read and write as inclusions. Data analysis using univariate and bivariate analysis with a chi-square test (α 0.05) was also carried out to see the effect of variable characteristics of respondents on the management of mask waste. **Results:** The study found no relationship between age, gender, education, and occupation in managing waste masks, but there was a significant effect between knowledge and waste management of disposable masks. **Conclusion:** The Health Office and local and regional apparatus are expected to provide comprehensive education through socialization or counseling to the community on how to properly manage disposable mask waste so as not to pollute the environment and misuse mask waste.

Keywords: knowledge, disposable mask, management

INTRODUCTION

Masks are a primary need during the *Covid-19* pandemic. Wearing a mask is one of the ways to prevent the spread of the *Covid-19* virus. One type of mask used by the community is a disposable mask. Wearing a mask has become a daily routine for many people. This has led to a significant increase in the demand for disposable face masks globally ⁽¹⁾ An increase in the use of single-use masks during a pandemic is occurring worldwide. Research conducted ⁽²⁾, the estimated daily use of masks in several countries in Asia reached 2,228,170,832 masks per day. The use of masks raises a

new problem: an increase in the waste generated by disposable masks.

According to the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, there has been an increase in medical waste by 30% - 50% during the *Covid-19* pandemic in Indonesia. Based on records from the Indonesian Institute of Sciences (LIPI), it is known that from March to September 2020, the amount of medical waste heap is estimated to be around 1,662.75 tons. The increased use of masks will cause the accumulation of mask waste, so it will most likely impact environmental pollution.

An article excerpt from the collaboration between UNPAD and ITB,

namely AMARI COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease Insight Applications 2019), medical masks or disposable masks made of polypropylene, a type of plastic. Plastic that decomposes will turn into microplastics and shrink into nanoplastics. The process of decomposition into microplastics produces toxins and organic pollutants. Microplastics ingested by marine biota can cause poisoning and even the death of aquatic organisms. In addition to microplastic, used mask waste can also trap animals in the water, making it difficult for animals to move ⁽³⁾

Based on the guidelines for the management of mask waste from the community, mask waste is not included in the category of medical waste, which is treated like medical waste in health facilities because it is not used in health services or patients in health facilities, so mask waste is categorized as domestic waste. Handling mask waste is carried out the same way as handling domestic waste. A situation in the community today is that masked waste is thrown away without taking it first. Improper management will cause new problems, such as improper disposal of mask waste can cause environmental damage.

The Ministry of Environment and Forestry has regulated the management of disposable masks from the community through Circular Letter No. 2 of 2020 and the Ministry of Health. Disposable mask waste management starts by collecting and separating mask waste from kitchen waste, spraying disinfectant on masks, changing the shape of masks before they are disposed of, wrapping mask waste in plastic bags and tied tightly, and washing hands after disposing of mask waste. ⁽⁴⁾ In a study conducted by Ruslinda et al. in 2020 in Padang, West Sumatra, 75.9% of *high-income* household respondents and 100% of *low-income* household respondents disposed of their medical masks by mixing them with other waste; 6.02% of respondents disposed of medical

masks in separate places; and 18%, *high-income* household respondents and 14% *middle-income* household respondents cut the mask first before throwing it away. ⁽⁵⁾

Based on the initial survey, it was found that most of the community did not know how to manage single-use mask waste. Used mask waste is still combined with other domestic waste without any prior treatment, such as separating mask waste, changing the mask's shape, carrying out disinfection, wrapping mask waste, and washing hands after handling mask waste. Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of respondents' characteristics on the management of disposable mask waste by households in the community in Tanjungpinang Barat Village.

METHODS

This type of research is analytic observational with a *cross-sectional* study design approach-retrieval of research data using survey methods by distributing questionnaires or questionnaires. The variables studied were age, gender, education, occupation, and waste management of masks by respondents. The research population is the productive age population of Tanjungpinang Barat Village, as many as 2557 families. The sample was taken using proportional random sampling, which was adjusted to the sample criteria of 346 families, with standards aged 15-64 years, willing to be respondents, and able to read and write. One person filled out the questionnaire to represent one family. Mask waste management data is categorized into two categories: eligible and not eligible. The research data were analyzed using univariate analysis with the presentation of the frequency distribution of all the variables studied. Bivariate analysis with a *chi-square* test ($\alpha = 0.05$) was also carried out to see the effect of variable characteristics of respondents on the management of mask waste.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

No	Respondent Characteristics	Waste Management		p-value	Contongency Coefficient Value
		MS	TMS		
1	Age				
	• 21-25	0	1	0.594	0.127
	• 26-30	0	22		
	• 31-35	1	52		
	• 36-40	0	73		
	• 41-45	0	52		
	• 46-50	0	18		
	• 51-55	0	50		
	• 56-60	0	18		
	Total	1	345		
2	Gender				
	• Female	1	303	0.710	0.020
	• Male	0	42		
	Total	1	345		
3	Education				
	• Primary School	0	7	0.965	0.028
	• Junior High School	0	34		
	• Senior High School	1	271		
	• Perguruan Tinggi	0	33		
	Total	1	345		
4	Profession				
	• Government Employees	0	16	0.995	0.025
	• Laborer	0	17		
	• Private	0	27		
	• Housewife	1	284		
	• Trader	0	1		
	Total	1	345		
5	Knowledge				
	• Good	1	0	0.006	0.145
	• Bad	40	305		
	Total	41	305		

Based on the table above, it is known that the majority of respondents are aged 36-40 years, with a total of 73 respondents aged 31-35 years and 41-45 years as 52 respondents, for ages 51-55 years as many as 50 respondents, while the age of 26 -30 as many as 22 respondents, aged 46-50 and 56-60 as many as 18 respondents while the least is at the age of 21-25 years with a total of 1 respondent. Almost all respondents managed to manage waste masks in a way that did not meet the requirements, namely 345 respondents; only one respondent aged 41-45 years who did the waste management

met the criteria. If the *p-value* is 0.594, or greater than α the one used (5%), then H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is not enough evidence to state that there is a significant relationship between the way of managing waste masks and age. The value of the contingency coefficient is 0.127, meaning that the relationship between the practice of mask waste management and generation is shallow and does not have a statistically significant association.

The age factor can affect a person's level of knowledge and is also influenced by internal factors consisting of education,

interests, experience, and age. Based on the results of the study, the majority of respondents were 36-40 years old. A person's grasping power with increasing age, a person's getting power and mindset will develop more. It should be at the age of 36-40 years that a person's grasping power and mindset increases because the older you get, the easier it is for someone to absorb information on how to manage mask waste. Information can also affect a person's knowledge. Someone with many sources of information will broaden his knowledge. However, in this study, respondents still lacked information regarding the management of mask waste, causing public ignorance in handling and managing disposable mask waste properly and correctly. ⁽⁶⁾ In theory, as a person's age increases, the level of knowledge, emotions, and beliefs that are more mature will increase, but in humans, of course, the increase in mental development processes is not as fast as a teenager. ⁽⁷⁾

The results of the analysis of the relationship between knowledge and practice of respondents are known to have a significant relationship. Knowledge can make someone aware so that they will behave according to their knowledge. Changes in behavior based on knowledge, awareness, and positive attitudes are lasting because they are based on their attention, not coercion. ⁽⁸⁾ Someone who understands well and comprehensively the management of domestic or household mask waste will be able to reduce mask waste as a source of the spread of the *COVID-19* virus, reducing the pollution of mask waste in the community and minimizing the misuse of mask waste by irresponsible people. Knowledge is a guide in shaping one's actions. ⁽⁸⁾

Gender in the table above is dominated by the female sex, with as many as 303 respondents who do not meet the requirements for waste management, and only one respondent who manages waste meets the requirements. The male

gender is only 42 respondents, and none of them do waste management that meets the requirements. The *p-value* is 0.710 or greater than α that used (5%). H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is not enough evidence to state a significant relationship between the way of managing waste masks and gender. The contingency coefficient value is 0.020, which means that the relationship between the practice of mask waste management and gender is shallow and does not have a statistically significant association.

The gender of the respondents in managing waste that does not meet the requirements, the majority are female. In theory, women are more concerned about the environment than men. ⁽⁹⁾ However, based on the results of interviews, respondents stated that they rarely leave the house, rarely gather with neighbors, and rarely listen to information from electronic media, so they do not know how to manage waste. Disposable masks properly before throwing them in the trash.

The majority of respondents have a high school education equivalent, namely as many as 271 respondents, for junior high school education, as many as 34 respondents, for tertiary education, as many as 33 respondents, and there are still respondents with final elementary education, namely seven respondents. Almost all respondents managed to mask waste in a way that did not meet the requirements, namely 345 respondents. Only one respondent with a high school education who did the mask waste management met the criteria. If the *p-value* of 0.965 or greater than α that used (5%), then H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is not enough evidence to state that there is a significant relationship between the way of managing waste masks and education. The contingency coefficient value is 0.028, meaning that the relationship between the practice of mask waste management and education is

shallow and does not have a statistically significant association.

This is because the educational background of the majority of respondents is SMA, SMP, and SD. In general, someone who is highly educated will have broader knowledge than someone with a low level of education. If someone's level of education is low, it will hinder the development of a person's attitude toward receiving information. ⁽⁷⁾ The information obtained about how to manage waste masks properly is still low. With the knowledge lacking in education, the actions taken are unsuitable for managing mask waste.

A person's knowledge of objects has different levels. ⁽⁷⁾ The knowledge factor about mask waste management must be instilled in school-level children so they can later become educators who convey information to other communities. One of the efforts made is to increase knowledge by way of counseling and training as a means of providing education so that they behave well in disposing of disposable masks ⁽¹⁰⁾

Based on occupation, most of the respondents, or 284 respondents, were housewives, 27 were private employees, 17 workers from labor, 16 were civil servants, and only one was a trader. Almost all respondents manage waste masks in a way that does not meet the requirements, namely 345 respondents, and only one respondent with a job as a housewife who works masks waste in the right way (qualifies). The *p-value* on the *Pearson Chisquare* is 0.995. This value is greater than α that used (5%). This means that H_0 is accepted, and it can be concluded that there is not enough evidence to state a significant relationship between managing waste masks and work. The contingency coefficient value is 0.025, meaning that the relationship between managing waste masks and work is shallow and does not have a statistically significant association.

Most respondents are homemakers who generally do not work, so they spend more time at home and lack information on correctly processing mask waste. Therefore, the role of the family and related sectors is still very much needed to improve the quality of time and create a more effective way of processing waste. So it is hoped that the role of the family in providing more support to family members is sufficient time to implement waste management in their daily lives. ⁽¹¹⁾

Statistical tests were conducted to determine the effect of knowledge on the management of mask waste, and it was found that only one respondent had good knowledge and managed waste in the right way (qualified). At the same time, no respondents had good knowledge and did not meet the requirements. Respondents who have poor knowledge but manage waste masks to meet their needs are known as many as 40 respondents. Respondents with inadequate knowledge and managing waste masks that do not meet the requirements are as many as 305 respondents. The *p-value* on the *Pearson Chisquare* is 0.006 or smaller than α that used (5%), so H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is sufficient evidence to state that there is a significant relationship between managing waste masks and the knowledge possessed by the respondents. The contingency coefficient value is 0.145, which means that the relationship between mask waste management and expertise is shallow but has a statistically significant association.

There is a relationship between managing mask waste and knowledge because most respondents have poor knowledge of working mask waste properly. Namely, 305 respondents were respondents who disposed of their mask waste mixed with other debris, and only one had good knowledge about mask waste management. However, some respondents still have a poor

understanding of managing mask waste properly.

The common knowledge of respondents in managing mask waste is also due to the lack of information obtained through socialization regarding the management of single-use mask waste, both from education and the mass media. This is in line with research.⁽¹²⁾ The lack of educational and socialization facilities causes public ignorance in handling and managing mask waste. Therefore, public knowledge needs to be increased through education and socialization regarding the steps for managing mask waste and the impact it causes because knowledge is a guide in shaping one's actions in doing something.⁽⁸⁾

This study is in line with research⁽¹³⁾. The results state that there is a relationship between knowledge and waste management of disposable masks by households with a *p-value* of 0.002.8, supported by research⁽¹⁴⁾. Namely, there is a connection between learning and waste management of shows during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Ministry of Environment and Forestry has regulated the control of disposable masks from the community through Circular Letter No. 2 of 2020 and the Ministry of Health. Disposable mask waste management starts by collecting and separating mask waste from kitchen waste, spraying disinfectant on masks, changing the shape of covers before they are disposed of, wrapping mask waste in plastic bags and tied tightly, and washing hands after disposing of mask waste.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research obtained from statistically processed data, it is known that there is no relationship between age, gender, education, and occupation in the way to manage waste masks, and there is a significant relationship between knowledge and how

to manage disposable masks.

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